

REDUCTION OF LEAKAGE CURRENT IN GRID-CONNECTED PV SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT:

Grid connections in the solar system have resulted in the revolution in the performance of the solar system and opened the doors of several opportunities to support the use of solar systems. The grid connected photovoltaic (PV) power systems are replacing the other systems very rapidly due to the better performance parameters like efficiency there by reducing the space requirement and cost of present systems. The grid connected system always faces the problems related to the safety and the job of the design engineer is to optimize the performance of the system. The decision makers have to work for addressing the issues related to the leakage current in such systems. Authors have discussed about the performance improvement by boost inverter inclusion in the conventional system. The near state pulse width modulation (NSPWM) is also included in the scope of this study under MATLAB /SIMULINK environment. The system performance was found improved hence the study is helpful for improvement of the solar systems connected to the grid.

KEYWORDS: PV- photo voltaic, PWM- pulse width modulation, cl-ssbi coupled inductor single boost inverter, NSPWM- near state pulse width modulation.

INTRODUCTION:

The world has found more suitable than other renewable resources for electricity generation. The huge capacity of generating the electricity without any pollution is very important aspect for the developing country like India. The solar systems are occupying the market worldwide very rapidly due to the vital features. The world is in need of clean sources and systems for sustainable development and solar systems fulfill all the requirements of such needs. The main aim of this project is to analyze and model of grid connected PV inverter systems with respect to reduce leakage current phenomenon that can damage solar panel and provide safety related to leakage current problem. New topologies and control strategies that will minimize leakage current reduce the size, cost and exhibit high efficiency is proposed and verified.

SIMULINK MODEL:

Figure 1: simulation diagram

Figure 2: Design of solar panel

The output current of grid connected PV system by using conventional pwm method is 0.2A and by using the nspwm method the output current is 0.9 A.

Figure 3: Converter with coupled inverter

Figure 6: Waveform of output voltage
 The output voltage of SIMULATION after applying the PV technique is 150 V

RESULTS OF SIMULATION:

Figure 4: Waveform of leakage current

The leakage current by using conventional pwm method in grid connected system is 1.5 mA and by using nspwm method the leakage current is 0.2 mA.

Figure 5: Waveform of output current

Figure 7: Waveform of THD

The output THD of conventional pwm method is 20.18% is reduced upto 10.91% by using nspwm technique.

CONCLUSION:

This paper has presented the reduction of leakage current in grid connected PV system. Diode D4 is added in the front of topology together with D1 to block the leakage current loop during the circuit operation. The leakage current caused due to the parasitic capacitance is reduced by using NSPWM technique. By using this technique in grid connected PV system, the output THD of the system can be reduced. The switching losses in PWM technique is can be reduced by using NSPWM up to then 33.33%. Also coupled inductor can improve the gain of the output. This helps in improving efficient grid output. The software tool used in this project is MATLAB 2012b.

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